

Histological Analysis of Preputial Circumcision Specimen: The Argument for and Against Neonatal Circumcision

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ABSTRACT

Background: Circumcision, the surgical removal of the prepuce, remains one of the most debated procedures worldwide. While it is advocated for its potential role in reducing sexually transmitted and urinary tract infections, it continues to be primarily driven by sociocultural and religious factors. The prepuce, however, is a specialised tissue with protective, sensory, and reconstructive functions, and its routine removal raises anatomical and ethical concerns. **Objective:** To evaluate the histological features of the neonatal prepuce excised during circumcision and also to assess its functional and surgical significance. **Methodology:** A prospective observational study was conducted between September and November 2024 at Immaculate Heart of Mary Specialist Hospital Nkpor, Anambra State, Nigeria. Thirty-six neonates undergoing circumcision by Plastibell or freehand method were recruited following informed parental consent. Excised prepuces were formalin-fixed, processed, stained with haematoxylin and eosin, and examined for epithelial structure, layer thickness, vascularity, and neural distribution. Data were analysed descriptively using SPSS. **Results:** Participants had a mean age of 14.6 ± 6.7 days and a mean weight of 3.6 ± 0.7 kg. Histology revealed five distinct layers: epidermis, dermis, Dartos fascia, lamina propria, and mucosa, with a mean thickness of 3.96 ± 0.95 mm. The lamina propria was highly vascularised (5–9 vessels/mm²), and nerve bundles were present in 86% of Dartos samples. Both epidermis and mucosa showed keratinised squamous epithelium with intact basement membranes. Inflammatory infiltrates were seen in 44% of specimens, but no dysplasia or malignancy was observed. **Conclusion:** The neonatal prepuce is a complex tissue with structural and functional importance. Routine circumcision lacks sufficient histological justification, warranting multidisciplinary review and public debate on its continued practice.

Keywords: Circumcision, Neonatal prepuce, Histology, Reconstructive significance.

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INTRODUCTION

Circumcision is the surgical removal of part or all of the prepuce, the layered mucocutaneous fold that covers and protects the glans penis.^{1,2,3,4} In males, it has become a widely tolerated practice. At the same time, in females, it has been outlawed globally and classified as female genital mutilation (FGM) due to its clear harms.^{2,3,10,11}

The procedure is performed across all age groups, from neonates and infants to older children and adults, with the strongest motivations being sociocultural and religious rather than medical.^{2,5,6,7} Although it is often claimed to serve a prophylactic function, such as reducing the risk of sexually transmitted infections (STIs), urinary tract infections (UTIs), and cervical cancer in female partners, as are frequently cited, they remain subjects of ongoing debate.^{1,2,8,9}

Circumcision has been described as one of the world's most controversial surgical procedures. First, the question of its indication persists. In most cases, it is not driven by medical necessity but by tradition and belief. Second, it is often performed on non-consenting individuals, neonates or young children, raising ethical concerns about autonomy and informed consent. These issues have led to declining access and acceptance in Europe and North America, even as the practice remains widespread in Africa and Asia, where cultural and religious traditions strongly sustain it.^{1,2,8,9}

A third, and often overlooked, source of controversy is the prepuce itself. Far from being redundant, the prepuce is a specialised tissue measuring 97–129 cm² when unfolded. It contains abundant nerve endings, vasculature, lymphatics, and apocrine glands that secrete pheromones. Its mucosal layer produces antimicrobial enzymes such as lysozyme, and the frenulum enables smooth gliding during intercourse.¹² Functionally, it protects the glans, contributes significantly to sexual function, and provides vital

reconstructive material for urological surgery, including repairs of hypospadias, epispadias, fistulae, and urethral strictures.¹² Yet, during routine circumcision, this unique tissue is excised and discarded—disrupting vascular, lymphatic, and neural networks, and raising profound questions about the wisdom of its removal.

Debates around circumcision have traditionally centred on risks and benefits, often neglecting the significance of what is being lost: the prepuce. To address this gap, it is essential to study the structure and function of this tissue, both for its role in human physiology and its value in surgical practice.

This study seeks to histologically evaluate neonatal prepuce specimens excised during circumcision. By highlighting the inherent properties of the prepuce, the findings aim to inform ongoing discussions on the medical, ethical, and surgical justification for routine neonatal circumcision.

METHODOLOGY

This study was designed as a prospective observational study involving male neonates undergoing circumcision. It was conducted at Immaculate Heart of Mary Specialist Hospital Nkpor, Anambra State, Nigeria, between September and November 2024 (10 weeks).

The research focused on analysing the prepuce (foreskin) excised during circumcision. Each specimen was examined both macroscopically and microscopically to assess its structural and histological features.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval was obtained from the Nnamdi Azikiwe University Teaching Hospital (NAUTH) Nnewi, Anambra State, NAUTH Health Research and Ethics Committee (NHREC) (NAUTH/CS/66/VOL.16/VER.3/95/2024/029). Written informed consent was obtained from each neonate's caregiver before recruitment.

Eligibility Criteria

Inclusion: All male neonates undergoing circumcision by either the Plastibell or freehand technique, whose caregivers provided informed consent.

Exclusion: Neonates undergoing repeat circumcision, those with congenital penile anomalies, or those whose caregivers declined consent.

Sample Size

The minimum sample size was calculated using a web-based sample size calculator (<https://www.calculator.net/sample-size-calculator.html>), applying the following parameters:

Confidence interval: 95%

Margin of error: 5%

Expected population proportion: 99%

Population size: infinite

The minimum required sample size was 16, but a total of 36 neonates were ultimately recruited to strengthen the reliability of findings.

Recruitment and Data Collection

Eligible neonates were consecutively enrolled and assigned a unique identifier (001–100). Circumcisions were carried out according to hospital protocol. During each procedure, the prepuce was excised in one piece, with the proximal end tagged using 5/0 vicryl for orientation.

A structured proforma was completed for each neonate, documenting demographic and clinical details. Variables recorded included age in days, weight in kilograms, prepuce thickness (mm), layer characteristics, distribution of neurovascular bundles, and the presence or absence of the balanopreputial membrane.

Tissue Processing and Histology

The excised prepuce was immediately fixed in 10% buffered formalin. Each specimen was grossly examined by a pathologist, then sectioned into proximal, middle, and distal zones.

Representative samples were processed into formalin-fixed paraffin-embedded (FFPE) tissue blocks following standard histological protocols: dehydration in graded alcohol (70%–100%), clearing in xylene, embedding in paraffin wax, sectioning into 4–5 μm ribbons using a microtome, and mounting onto glass slides and drying in a warm oven. Slides were stained using Haematoxylin and Eosin (H&E). This involved: deparaffinisation in xylene, rehydration in descending grades of alcohol, nuclear staining with haematoxylin, cytoplasmic counterstaining with eosin, dehydration, clearing, and mounting with resin and coverslip. The prepared slides were examined using a Leica DM1000 binocular microscope with an in-built digital camera. Observations included: thickness of mucosal and skin layers, estimated nerve and vascular density, and morphological characteristics of each preputial layer.

Data Analysis

All data were entered into SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences, ver23) for analysis. Continuous variables (e.g., prepuce thickness) were summarised as means and standard deviations. In contrast, categorical variables (e.g., presence of balanopreputial membrane) were expressed as frequencies and percentages. Results were presented in tables, charts, and representative micrographs.

RESULTS

A total of thirty-six (36) male neonates were recruited for this study. All underwent circumcision, and their excised prepuces were processed for histological analysis. The mean age of participants was 14.6 ± 6.7 days, and the mean weight was 3.6 ± 0.7 kg.

Histological examination confirmed that the neonatal prepuce is a complex structure comprising five distinct layers: epidermis, dermis, Dartos fascia, lamina propria, and mucosa, with an overall mean thickness of 3.96 ± 0.95 mm. The

thickness of individual layers ranged as follows: epidermis (0.10–0.50 mm), dermis (0.20–1.30 mm), Dartos fascia (1.00–4.00 mm), lamina propria (0.20–2.00 mm), and mucosa (0.10–0.40 mm) (Table 1). Representative photomicrographs (Plates 1–3) illustrate the five layers and their vascular and connective tissue profiles.

Vascular analysis revealed that the epidermis and mucosa were avascular. In contrast, the dermis, Dartos fascia, and lamina propria demonstrated vascular densities of 1–4, 3–8, and 5–9 vessels/mm², respectively (Table 2). Notably, the lamina propria emerged as the most vascularized zone.

The epidermis was consistently lined by keratinized squamous epithelium with an average of nine cell layers, lacking a basement membrane. In contrast, the mucosa exhibited keratinized squamous epithelium supported by a basement membrane, with a mean thickness of 9.9 ± 2.8 cell layers.

Other key findings included the presence of hair follicles in 63.9% of dermal samples, nerve bundles in 19% of the dermis and 86% of the Dartos fascia, and predominantly compact connective tissue in the dermis (77.8%) versus

loose connective tissue in the lamina propria (88.9%) (Tables 2).

Importantly, no evidence of metaplasia or malignancy was detected. However, inflammatory infiltrates were observed in 44.4% of specimens, likely reflecting procedural trauma.

Table 1. Thickness of layers of removed prepuce

Layers	Average thickness (SD)	Min	Max
Average thickness of prepuce in mm	3.96 (± 0.95)	2.10	5.80
Average thickness of preputial Epidermis in mm	0.20 (± 0.12)	0.10	0.50
Average thickness of preputial Dermis in mm	0.67 (± 0.26)	0.20	1.30
Average thickness of preputial Dartos in mm	2.27 (± 0.85)	1.00	4.00
Average thickness of preputial Lamina Propria in mm	0.88 (± 0.38)	0.20	2.00
Average thickness of preputial Mucosa in mm	0.15 (± 0.08)	0.10	0.40

Figure 1. Micrograph of the proximal third: sections show normal prepuce with the five layers including SE- surface epithelium (glabrous skin); Dermis; Dartos muscle layer; lamina propria and mucosa. V= vessel; M= muscle; ME= mucosa epithelium (HE x100)

Figure 2. Micrograph of the middle third of the preputial specimen. Section of prepuce showing the 5 distinct layers with hair follicle noted in the dermis. V - blood vessel

Figure 3. Micrograph of distal third of the prepuce: Sections show normal prepuce with the five layers including SE- surface epithelium (glaborous skin); Dermis; Dartos muscle layer; lamina propria and mucosa. V= vessel; M= muscle; ME= mucosa epithelium (HE x100)

Table 2. Structures in the layers of the prepuce

Layers	Structures	Mean (SD)	frequency	percentage
Epidermis	Vessels per mm ²	0	-	-
	Epithelial cell type - Squamous	-	36	100%
	Sub-class of epithelium: Keratinized	-	36	100%
	Basement membrane	-	0	-
	Gross Appearance – transverse folds	-	36	100%
	Number of epithelial cell layers	9.2 (± 2.40)	-	-
Dermis	Vessels per mm ²	2.22 (± 0.87)	1 (min)	4 (max)
	Hair Follicle - Yes	-	23	63.9%
	- No	-	13	36.1%
	Nerve bundle - Yes	-	7	19.4%
	- No	-	29	80.6%
	Blood vessels - Yes	-	36	100%
	- No	-	0	0%
	Reticular / Papillary distinction	-	36	100%
	Connective Tissue Arrangement:	-	-	-
- Compact	-	28	77.8%	
- Loose	-	8	22.2%	
Dartos	Vessels per mm ²	4.97 (± 1.42)	3 (min)	8 (max)
	Blood Vessels - Yes	-	36	100%
	- No	-	0	0%
	Nerve bundles - Yes	-	31	86.1%
	- No	-	5	13.9%

	Connective Tissue arrangement:			
	- Compact		0	0%
	- Loose		36	100%
Lamina Propria	Vessels per mm ²	6.58 (± 1.08)	5 (min)	9 (max)
	Blood vessels - yes		36	100%
	- No		0	0%
	Nerve Bundle - Yes		19	52.8%
	- No		17	47.2%
	Connective Tissue Arrangement:			
	- Compact		4	11.1%
	- Loose		32	88.9%
Mucosa	Vessels per mm ²	-	-	-
	Epithelial Cell Types - Squamous		36	100%
	Sub-class of epithelial - Keratinized		36	100%
	Basement membrane - Yes		36	100%
	Folds - Yes		36	100%
	Number of Epithelial cell layers	9.9 (± 2.80)	6 (min)	19 (max)

DISCUSSION

Neonatal circumcision has been in practice since the antiquity. The discussion has always centred on the indications, benefits, complications and contra-indications. There has been little or no discussion on what is lost in neonatal circumcision - the real victim of the procedure, the prepuce.

The prepuce is a thick layer of skin, Dartos and mucosa. It has a distinct 5 layers. The average thickness is 4mm. This is an addition of 8mm to the thickness of the neonatal glans and distal penis. It contributes to the overall diameter and thickness of the adult penis.¹³ The thickness of the skin of the human body ranges from 0.5mm for the eyelid to 4mm for the upper back. This is for epidermis and dermis only. Therefore, at a mean of 0.77mm, the preputial skin is close to the skin of the eyelid in thickness, 0.8 to 1.2mm. The eyelid resembles the prepuce in structure and in function - which is protection.¹⁴ The arrangement of the preputial structure and its thickness emphasize the role it is to play beyond adding to the girth of the penis. According to Fahmy MAB,⁴ the mucosa of the inner prepuce is lined by stratified squamous epithelium, similar to the frictional mucosa of the vagina, the inner eyelid, the mouth, and the oesophagus. This mucosal aspect of the prepuce has a great capacity for self-repair.⁴ The

intervening layers of Dartos provides a cushioning plane for the aforementioned skin and mucosa.

The neonatal prepuce showed no evidence of gross anomaly in this study. There was no metaplasia or malignancy. Sixteen percent showed evidence of acute inflammatory cells invasion. This may be attributed to the crushing and traumatic effect during the process of circumcision. Apart from congenital anomalies, the human prepuce is predisposed to acquired anomalies like other skin and tissues. There may be phimosis, paraphimosis, balanitis, balamoposthitis, preputial cysts, lichen sclerosus, balanitis plasmacellularis, excess smegma accumulation etc.¹⁵ The prepuce may be disposed to Lichen Sclerosus (LS), which is a chronic inflammation and may lead to phimosis and increased risk of cancer.^{16,17} These studies leading to this conclusion were done in adults. Moreover, they are acquired conditions that are preventable. Hence there is no guarantee that a neonatal prepuce will ever develop these.

In a Study by Tokgoz *et al.*, foreskin samples from individuals with phimosis often exhibit chronic inflammatory changes, including subepidermal fibrosis and lymphocytic infiltration. These changes contribute to the inelasticity of the foreskin, perpetuating the condition. This study

was carried out to evaluate the dermatopathology of the preputium in preschool and primary school children. They concluded that the presence of foreskin in preschool and primary school children might rarely be associated with important inflammatory dermatoses like lichen sclerosus et atrophicus (LSA) even in the absence of phimosis.¹⁸ Therefore, the prepuce is a normal part of the body, not to be despised. Again phimosis, is an acquired condition that is preventable. And with improving care for the prepuce and medical treatment for it, the tide can be stemmed on this condition.

Balanitis plasma cellularis also known as Zoon's balanitis, presents histologically with a dense plasma cell infiltrate in the dermis, spongiosis, and epidermal atrophy. It primarily affects uncircumcised men and is thought to result from chronic irritation and poor hygiene.^{19,20} This is an acquired disease of adult prepuce which is not being well cared for.

Excess smegma accumulation can be a problem of the prepuce with its attendant consequences. Smegma is a combination of shed epithelial cells, skin oils, and moisture. While it serves as a lubricant, excessive accumulation can lead to inflammation and infection. Histologically, smegma consists of keratin debris and can harbor bacteria and fungi, contributing to conditions like balanitis.²¹

In this study, the Lamina Propria, Dartos and Dermis are vascularized. The degree of vascularity decreases as one approaches distally. The lamina propria is the most vascularized of the three planes, followed by the Dartos. The two being contiguous shows the vascular predilection for the inner prepuce. In their study on the microvessel density of control and hypospadiac prepuce, Elbakry *et al.* noted a variation in the microvessel density of the inner and outer prepuce.²² They recognized that there are more microvessel density at the inner prepuce compared to the outer region. The layers of the prepuce from outside to inside are epidermis,

dermis, Dartos, lamina Propria and mucosa. The inner layer will correspond to mucosa, lamina Propria and Dartos layers. This is in keeping with the findings in this study where we have high vascular density at the Dartos and the Lamina Propria layers. Prasad *et al.*²² concluded that the inner and outer layers of the prepuce can be equally used for neourethra and hypospadias repair on the basis of their vascularity.²² Therefore we have a tissue that is useful to the surgeon in all its layers. In their study Dossanova *et al.* noted that the prepuce is well vascularized and showed an increase in the number of vein clusters in the prepuce of the penis with age.²³ There is also an increase in the incidence of vessel wall fibrosis increased with age in that study.²³ Our study did not assess persons beyond the neonatal period. It also did not look at the intima of the vessels. However, being neonatal specimen, there may be no room to expect vascular fibrosis as this occurs with aging and exposure to toxic condition.

In this study, the density of blood vessels in the Dartos and lamina Propria ranges from 5 to 7 per mm². It is similar to the findings in a "systemic review and meta-analysis on macrovascular and microvascular anatomy of preputial skin in hypospadias and its implication" by Agrawal *et al.*²⁴ In their study, they found that microvessel density (MVD) was significantly lower in hypospadias (pooled mean, 28.85/HPF) versus controls (pooled mean, 45.46/HPF), correlating with severity of hypospadias. They also noted that the MVD varied a lot across different population worldwide.²⁴ Now the MVD for the normal prepuce of 45.46/HPF is similar to the finding in this study (5 to 7 per mm²). A 20-25/HPF is equivalent to 5 vessels/mm². Hence, in our study, MVD converted to HPF is 25-35/HPF. We had earlier noted in the study by Dossanova *et al.* that vasculature density increases with age.²³ Our study was conducted among neonates while the study by Agrawal *et al.* involves older children hence accounting for the difference in the final figure for the microvascular density. And for the

prepuce in our study to have a higher MVD than those with hypospadias in the systematic review and meta-analysis by Agrawal *et al.*, shows that the neonatal prepuce removed during circumcision is a normal tissue.

There is a variable presence of nerve bundles in the three layers above. It could be explained by the type of staining done (H&E), the zone sampled and the magnification used (which is x10). There is bound to be “skipped or missed areas” of importance. The type of staining and magnification was unable to pick the commonly mentioned sensory receptors: Meissner corpuscle, Pacinian corpuscles and free nerve endings. These specialized sensory receptors are responsible for detecting fine touch, vibration, and temperature. Cepada-Emiliano *et al.* in their study agreed that the patterns of density and distribution of neural tissue in the human penis, including the prepuce, are not fully characterized, and therefore the effects of the removal of the penile prepuce on penile sexual sensation are controversial. This assertion is based on immunohistochemical staining.²⁵

There was no special histological structure in the prepuce in this study. However, there is an average of nine (9) epithelial cells layers in the epidermis of the prepuce of these neonates. In a study by Ya-Xian *et al.* the genital skin has a mean epithelial cell layer of 6 ± 2 .²⁶ The study noted that there is an increase in the number of the epithelial cells with age. Considering that our study was on the neonate, it is expected that the epithelial cell layers will keep increasing with age.

This study showed that the preputial epidermis is of a keratinized squamous epithelium. However, it has no basement membrane. The mucosa is also of a keratinized squamous epithelium, but has basement membrane. The basement membrane provides structural support to the epithelial layers, provides selective barriers, cellular interactions, tissue organization, mechanical support and organ development. Hence the mucosa of the prepuce is well supported and

protective against spread of infection and malignancy.²⁷

The Arguments for and Against Neonatal Circumcision

Those who argue for neonatal circumcision is of the opinion that it is a socio-cultural practice that initiates a male child into the society whose deviant will be an out-cast in the society which could be psychologically traumatic. Gollaher D. in his paper, “From ritual to science: The medical transformation of circumcision in America”, said: “Circumcision persisted, despite there being no scientific evidence of its efficacy, because physicians and patients continued to reinforce its social meaning long after the original theories that inspired it were discredited”.²⁸

Neonatal circumcision is being promoted in the medical world as a prophylaxis for urinary tract infection (UTI), sexually transmitted infections (STIs), HIV/AIDS transmission, and human papilloma virus.²⁹ These are flawed arguments. There is no documented epidemics of UTI in uncircumcised boys. With good hygiene, these acquired conditions can be ameliorated. No attempt has been made to excise other body areas with higher micro-organism load such as anorectum, vagina, oral cavity and axilla. Besides these bacteria are part of the human microbiome.^{30,31} Demir *et al.* noted less bacteria in boys with smegma than in those without smegma, meaning that smegma may be protective.³² They also noted lower infection rate after circumcision despite the bacteria in preputial space.

The medical indications as an argument for neonatal circumcision is flawed as most if not all can be treated non-operatively, and most are not life-threatening. As events evolved, there is hardly any absolute medical indication for circumcision except for Balanitis Xerotica Obliterans (BXO), and cancer.^{8,33,34}

Studies have been conducted to show that there is no affectation of sexual function in the males that were circumcised.^{35,36} This conclusion is founded on observing no difference in fine touch sensation

on the glans. The opponents argued that the glans/penis is a primitive sexual organ, not primed for tactile and temperature sensation. Others have also argued that indeed there is an affectation in length and girth of the penis by circumcision.^{13,37} They are reduced. The trauma of neonatal circumcision is thought to stunt the growth rate in length and reduce effectively also the girth. Cold and Taylor posited that circumcision removes 50% of the penile skin with its nervous components, thereby altering the sensory experiences.³

The proponents of neonatal circumcision have no regard for the prepuce excised during circumcision. The lost prepuce is considered a dispensable tissue. The **prepuce (foreskin)** is a valuable tissue in reconstructive and plastic surgery due to its unique anatomical and physiological characteristics. It has found use in several surgeries: labioplasty, vaginoplasty, clitoral hood reconstruction, eyelid surgery, skin graft nose and lip reconstruction etc.³⁸

Neonatal circumcision raises complex ethical and public health questions, particularly regarding age and the lack of informed consent from the client. **Proponents of neonatal circumcision argues that it ensures a population-level sexually transmitted infection (STI) reduction; thereby** potentially lowering community-wide transmission rates of HIV and HPV. Hence the child participates and sacrifices for the community good. It also by this, makes for **cost-effectiveness** by reducing long-term healthcare costs related to STIs and urinary tract infections.^{39,40,41} Critics argue that elective, irreversible procedures should be deferred until the individual can participate in the decision.^{42,43} Ultimately, the ethical debate hinges on balancing immediate medical and public health benefits with the rights of the child to bodily autonomy and future choice.

The proponents of neonatal circumcision argue that it is technically simpler, safer, faster, and less expensive than when performed later in life.⁴⁴

This argument will hold if we accept that circumcision is indicated in the first place.

In conclusion, the prepuce is a uniquely created tissue in the body. It has a rich neurovascular supply. There is nothing clinically, grossly, histologically and microbiological wise that suggests that the prepuce is a redundant tissue or poses a threat to the male child. Neonatal circumcision, and indeed circumcision, has not justified its continued practice. All the arguments for the continual practice of neonatal circumcision cannot stand in the face of intense scrutiny.

We recommend therefore, a joint cultural, medical and scientific review of the continual practice of this procedure. A public debate and advocacy should be vigorously pursued on this.

Authors Roles

VIM: conceptual development, design of the study, acquisition of data, as well as analysis and interpretation of data; also in drafting and critically revising the work for intellectual content, **FEM:** Design of the study, acquisition of data and drafting the work for intellectual content. **CCO:** design of the study and acquisition of data. **COO:** Design of the study, acquisition of data, drafting and revising the work for intellectual content. **FCA:** Design of the study, acquisition of data and drafting the work for intellectual content.. All the authors revised the article, gave approval for the final version to be published and agreed to be accountable for all aspects of the work.

Conflict of interest

We declare no conflict of interest with relation to this work.

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